

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Affective Forecasting in Elections: A Socio-Communicative Perspective

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In orienting themselves to the future, people form expectations not only on what will happen but also on how they will feel about possible future occurrences. So far, such affective forecasting—the prediction of future feelings—has been studied mainly from a psychological perspective. This study aims to show the importance of a socio-communicative perspective for understanding the predictors, manifestations, and consequences of affective forecasting, especially when collective futures are at stake. Using the case study of the 2019–2021 Israeli elections and a combination of a 12-wave survey and 25 focus groups, we show how political affective forecasts are associated with socio-communicative factors, are used in social interactions, and have consequences for political polarization and participation. We conclude with a discussion of the implications of our findings for future research on affective forecasting in communication studies.

Keywords: Affect, Electoral Projections, Polarization, Political Communication, Social Identity

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Introduction

Projections about the future play a key role in people's individual and collective lives. Constructing scenarios of events that have yet to occur—from mundane activities such as exercising and shopping to the selection of a life partner or a national leader—helps people navigate towards or away from imagined futures (Gilbert & Wilson, 2007; Tenenboim-Weinblatt, 2018). A crucial component of this process is Affective Forecasting (AF), namely, “people's predictions about their future feelings” (Wilson & Gilbert, 2003, p. 345). Attempting to predict how various experiences will make us feel facilitates decision-making on which futures to pursue or try to avoid. Beyond the private domain (e.g., marriage; Lavner et al., 2013), such affective projections are also pertinent to the public–political realm. Citizens who imagine how they might feel about being exposed to opposing political views (Dorison et al., 2019), or about different elections outcomes (Norris et al.,

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2011), can adjust their political behavior in order to achieve affectively desirable outcomes.

Rooted in psychological research, AF studies have mostly focused on the cognitive mechanisms that shape individuals' predictions, often leading to inaccurate assessments (e.g., [Lench et al., 2019](#); [Wilson & Gilbert, 2003, 2005](#)). However, this perspective largely ignores the communicative-collective nature of projecting uncertain futures ([Kay & King, 2020](#); [Szpunar & Szpunar, 2016](#)), and especially political futures ([Grusin, 2010](#); [Neiger, 2007](#)). Furthermore, it sidesteps the effect of future-oriented evaluations on present behaviors ([Aspinwall, 2005](#)), irrespective of their accuracy. In political communication research, recent surges of attention to both electoral forecasts (e.g., [Tenenboim-Weinblatt, 2018](#); [Westwood et al., 2020](#)) and affect (e.g., [Iyengar et al., 2019](#), [Lecheler, 2018](#); [Wahl-Jorgensen, 2019](#)) have overlooked the crucial links between the two phenomena. This article aims to address these gaps. Focusing on election projections, it provides a multifaceted examination of the socio-communicative predictors, interactional uses, and political consequences of AF, as a first step in bringing the study of AF into communication research.

To this end, we focus on the rich case study of the 2019–2021 Israeli elections, relying on a combination of surveys and focus groups. This mixed-method approach allows us to study AF at the individual, interactional, and aggregate social levels and to contribute to both political and interpersonal communication research. Specifically, we focus on three interlocking domains: (a) Identity—the role of social identities in shaping affective forecasts at the individual level, their use for identity work in political discourse at the interactional level, and the emergence of polarized affective forecasts at the societal level; (b) Media—the role of exposure to politically congruent media in shaping affective forecasts; and (c) Mobilization—the motivating power of AF and how it is linked to political participation. We conclude with an integrative discussion of the findings and their implications for future research on AF in communication studies.

Theoretical Background

Affective Forecasting in Psychological Research: Definitions and Limitations

In psychology, AF is defined as “predicting one’s own future feelings” ([Kushlev & Dunn, 2012](#), p. 277). These predictions can refer to the duration, intensity, and valence (positivity/negativity) of the future affect ([Wilson & Gilbert, 2003](#)). Originating in happiness studies and earlier work on “hedonic forecasting” ([Kahneman & Snell, 1992](#)), research in this area has usually addressed people’s general satisfaction, understanding affect broadly as the “superordinate category for valenced states” ([Gross, 1998](#), p. 273). This perspective, which we adopt in this study, regards affect as inclusive of more specific emotions (for a similar approach in communication studies, see [Papacharissi, 2015](#); for a review of the concepts of affect and emotion, see [Wahl-Jorgensen, 2019](#)).

Existing AF studies have mostly asked individuals to gauge how (un)happy they would feel if certain events were to occur, subsequently comparing their affective forecasts to actually experienced affect. In this strand of research, scholars have identified a variety of biases in AF, most notably the “impact bias,” where people overestimate the intensity of their reactions to future events, from getting rich or achieving tenure to the loss of one’s sports team or presidential candidate (see reviews in [Norris et al., 2011](#); [Wilson & Gilbert, 2003, 2005](#)).

Many such errors stem from differences between the contexts surrounding present forecasts and future affective experiences ([Gilbert & Wilson, 2007](#); [Kahneman et al., 2006](#)), including socio-communicative contexts, such as framing ([Wilson & Gilbert, 2003](#)) or “collective exuberance” following electoral success ([Norris et al., 2011](#), p. 243). However, the role of information sources and social interactions in such processes has not been explored. Moreover, while research has documented the influence of both sociodemographic (e.g., age; [Scheibe et al., 2011](#)) and psychological factors (e.g., emotional intelligence; [Dunn et al., 2007](#)) on AF, the role of social-political identities in shaping affective forecasts has received scant attention. Likewise, and owing to the primarily experimental approach of existing research, little is known about people’s actual uses of AF in social communication.

Perhaps most surprising is the lack of empirical research on the behavioral implications of AF. The motivational potential of affective forecasts has been an underlying assumption of AF research: imagining how one would feel about different scenarios can contribute to “making people work hard to obtain things that they predict will have large positive consequences and avoid things that they predict will have large negative consequences” ([Wilson & Gilbert, 2005](#), p. 134). Nevertheless, there has been little systematic research into the behavioral implications of AF. This study thus builds on central conceptual and theoretical insights developed in psychological research, but moves beyond psychology’s focus on experimental methods and AF’s accuracy. Specifically, it examines how AF is associated with socio-communicative factors, used in social interactions, and mobilizes people for political participation.

Affective Forecasting, Social Identities, and Political Polarization

Looking at social-political identities is a first step in understanding the socio-communicative factors shaping affective expectations about political futures. Affect is inherent to the concept of social identity, defined as “an individual’s self-concept which derives from his knowledge of his membership of a social group (or groups) together with the value and emotional significance attached to that membership” ([Tajfel, 1978](#), p. 63). A growing body of scholarship has emphasized the crucial role of political identities—as viewed from the perspective of social identity theory – in democratic life and political communication processes ([Cramer Walsh, 2004](#); [Kreiss et al., 2020](#)). The close relation between affect and social-political identities has proved particularly useful in understanding political polarization, and especially

Affective Polarization (AP), referring to people's increasingly negative feelings toward political out-group members, compared to positive feelings toward their political ingroup (Iyengar et al., 2012, 2019; Reiljan, 2020).

Collective political identities regularly revolve around shared hopes and future aspirations (Linz & Stepan, 1992). At the level of political identification, present identities are interwoven with imaginations and evaluations of future scenarios—as is evidenced in the use of future-oriented social distance measures in AP studies. To answer questions such as “Suppose a son or daughter of yours was getting married. How would you feel if he or she married a supporter of the _____ party?” (Almond & Verba, 1963, p. 532), people need to imagine the described scenario and assess how they might feel if it were to materialize, thereby engaging in AF.

Drawing on such social distance measures and on feeling thermometers, scholars have documented worldwide political cleavages (Iyengar et al., 2012, Reiljan, 2020; Shamir et al., 2017). While AF regarding prospective election outcomes has rarely been studied, the same cleavages might shape people's appraisals of alternative future trajectories. Accordingly, when election candidates are associated with entrenched social identities, future outcomes desired by one political camp would be dreaded by the other. Examining the relation between identity-based ideology and AP, Mason (2018) found that Americans who positioned themselves further to either side of the ideological scale (extremely conservative/extremely liberal) scored higher on various social-distance measures and had more polarized feelings toward the political ingroup and out-group. In shifting the focus to AF in the Israeli context—where the primary political cleavage has been historically between the right and the left (Shamir et al., 2017)—we similarly expect that people who identify more strongly with either camp will forecast stronger feelings about prospective election outcomes. Accordingly, we hypothesize that:

H1a The more people's political identities tend towards the right or the left, the stronger they expect to feel about the materialization of their electoral projections.

H1b The more people's political identities tend towards the right or the left, the more polarized their affective forecasts are in relation to candidates from their own and others' political camps.

Furthermore, political identities are socially negotiated through socio-affective interactions. Identity work, through which “talk makes available to participants and observers who the people doing the talk must be” (Tracy & Robles, 2013, p. 7), is a central element of everyday conversation, and political discussion in particular. As demonstrated by Cramer (2016; Cramer Walsh, 2004), social identities enable people to make sense of politics: in discussing current events, as well as hopes and fears for the future, people's definition of who they are is central to how they interact with others and understand the political world.

Affective discursive strategies are essential to such social interactions and the identity work underlining them. As Parrott (2003, p. 29) explained, positioning oneself can be achieved by displaying “the emotions that are characteristic of one’s position,” while positioning one’s opponents can be accomplished by characterizing their feelings as inappropriate. The close relations between affect and sociopolitical positioning have also been demonstrated in studies of online political discussions. For instance, researchers examined AP by analyzing sentiment expressions in ingroup and cross-group interactions (Yarchi *et al.*, 2021), and showed how the evolution of such affective discourse is associated with changing political evaluations (González-Bailón *et al.*, 2012). To understand AF’s possible interactional uses for establishing in-/out-groups and negotiating political identities, we thus ask:

RQ1 Do people use affective forecasts for political identity work in social interactions, and in what ways?

Given the plausible relations between AF and political identities, we expect that the overall social distribution of affective forecasts will be polarized. That is, most people would expect to be very happy about a victory of their preferred candidates and very unhappy about an expected defeat, resulting in a bimodal distribution—a prime marker of polarization (DiMaggio *et al.*, 1996; Fiorina & Abrams, 2008).¹ We thus hypothesize that:

H2a Affective forecasts about political candidates have a polarized distribution.

In practice, however, the level of polarization might depend on the specific nature of predicted outcomes, owing to the combination of two biases—namely, people’s inclination to form forecasts based on available experiences (Gilbert & Wilson, 2007; Tversky & Kahneman, 1973) and in accordance with their political preferences (i.e., wishful thinking; Krizan *et al.*, 2010). Thus, people should be able to anticipate an incumbent’s victory more readily than a challenger victory—both when they expect to be happy and unhappy about such an outcome—as it is easier to imagine a continuation of the present. A challenger victory might be imagined mostly by those who prefer this outcome and are thus motivated to imagine it. Accordingly, we hypothesize that polarization would be asymmetric:

H2b Affective forecasts about expected political outcomes are more polarized in relation to incumbent leaders than to challengers.

Affective Forecasting and Media Exposure

Beyond its role in interpersonal communication, AF may be shaped by and through the media. Public opinion theories have long underscored the role of the media in informing expectations. According to Noelle-Neumann (1974), for instance, people scan the information environment for assessing the present and future climate of opinion. While present- and future-oriented perceptions are usually highly

correlated, the latter, she argues, are more significant in shaping behaviors. Various communication sources, such as mediated polls and campaigns, inform peoples' expectations regarding the electoral behaviors of in- and out-groups (Perryman et al., 2020), and possibly their own behavior. Examples of such media-driven dynamics in future-oriented public opinion include the “bandwagon” and “underdog” effects (e.g., Mutz, 1998; Stolwijk et al., 2016), alongside broader processes involving self-fulfilling and self-defeating electoral expectations (Rothschild & Malhotra, 2014; Tenenboim-Weinblatt, 2018). Notably, this body of work also points to the importance of affect in the relationships between media exposure and expectation-based public opinion processes—from Noelle-Neumann's (1974) “fear of isolation” to anxiety and enthusiasm as mediating the influence of poll exposure (Stolwijk et al., 2016).

While the prevalence of overt AF in media discourse is unknown, the prominence of future scenarios, evaluations, and affective dimensions in news discourse is well documented (see Lecheler, 2018; Neiger & Tenenboim-Weinblatt, 2018; Wahl-Jorgensen, 2019). The media thus serve as a vital source against which future-oriented affective assessments can be constructed. Studies of political polarization suggest that partisan news media play a particularly important role in shaping affective assessments. Multiple studies have established the link between AP and selective exposure to likeminded media sources, suggesting mechanisms ranging from motivated reasoning and identity activation to perceived opinion climate and acceptance of ideological media frames (Garrett et al., 2014; Tsfaty & Chotiner, 2016; Tsfaty & Nir, 2017).

Similarly, AP has been shown to be associated with exposure to political campaigns, which tend to portray out-group competitors unfavorably, thereby activating partisan identities and increasing contrast effects between candidates (Banks et al., 2021; Iyengar et al., 2012). In contemporary mediascapes, political campaigns heavily rely on social media (Kreiss et al., 2018), with candidates' own accounts as dominant and influential platforms (McLaughlin & Macafee, 2019). We can therefore suspect that exposure to both ideological news outlets and social media of ingroup political candidates will be associated with stronger and more polarized affective forecasts, above and beyond the role of ideological identification. Accordingly, we hypothesize that:

H3a People who are exposed to politically congruent news and social media sources during election campaigns have stronger affective forecasts about the materialization of their projections.

H3b: People who are exposed to politically congruent news and social media sources have more polarized affective forecasts.

Affective Forecasting and Political Participation

Lastly, we investigate AF's behavioral implications. Despite the pertinent argument that affective forecasts can serve as motivators for action, aimed at bringing about

desirable futures (Wilson & Gilbert, 2005; see also Aspinwall, 2005), this assumption has rarely been empirically explored to date, and to our knowledge, not in the context of political behavior. Just as expecting to feel good motivates physical exercising (Ruby *et al.*, 2011), the way people expect to feel about political futures might motivate them to engage politically, including the basic democratic act of turning out to vote. Indeed, a growing body of literature has documented the crucial role of affect and emotion in motivating political participation (e.g., Marcus, 2010; Papacharissi, 2015; Valentino *et al.*, 2011; Wahl-Jorgensen, 2019). Underlying much of this literature is the view of cognitive and affective processes as mutually shaping democratic engagement (Marcus, 2010). Linking this insight to the premise of AF theory, we hypothesize that:

H4a The more intensely people expect to feel about electoral outcomes the more they are inclined to vote.

While both expected positive and negative feelings should motivate election participation, optimism, which relies on confidence that desired outcomes are feasible, is known to be a stronger motivator than pessimism (Carver *et al.*, 2010). Accordingly, we hypothesize that:

H4b People who expect to be happy about the electoral outcomes are more inclined to vote than people who expect to be unhappy about the outcomes.

Furthermore, also the distance between AF concerning preferred and non-preferred outcomes might be associated with people's motivation for political participation. Research has shown that higher AP is associated with higher turnout, since the stakes for the elections are perceived as higher (Abramowitz & Stone, 2006; Ward and Tavits, 2019). Accordingly, we posit:

H4c The more polarized people's affective forecasts are, the more they are inclined to vote.

Finally, AF may also be used in communicative efforts to encourage political participation. If affective forecasts have motivating power (H4a–c) and they are presumably shaped by evaluative and future-oriented messages in public-mediated communication (H3a–b), individuals may also employ AF in their own social interactions to try and mobilize others. Such efforts are particularly relevant in political contexts, given the importance of social interactions for political participation, and specifically voter mobilization (Hooghe, 2016). We thus ask:

RQ2 Do people use affective forecasts in political interactions for mobilization purposes, and in what ways?

A summary of the study's 11 hypotheses and research questions is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Socio-Communicative Process of Political Affective Forecasting

Methods

Case

To address our research questions and hypotheses, we examined people's forecasts about the four rounds of the 2019–2021 Israeli elections. As events with well-defined possible outcomes and far-reaching social implications, elections involve intense forecasting efforts by various actors (Strömbäck, 2012; Tenenboim-Weinblatt, 2018), alongside heightened emotions fueled by political campaigns and identity-based polarization processes (Brader, 2006; Iyengar et al., 2019). Elections thus constitute a valuable setting for studying AF, and particularly its socio-communicative dimensions. Most AF studies have focused on the binary U.S. political system (e.g., Norris et al., 2011; Scheibe et al., 2011). The Israeli multiparty system permits studying AF in relation to a relatively complex, hard-to-predict competition (Fuchs, 2017), where the eventual identity of the prime minister (PM) depends on both electoral outcomes and ensuing coalition negotiations. The four successive elections provide a unique opportunity to examine AF over time, under conditions of major uncertainty and evolving emotions, and in relation to changing electoral outcomes.

The initial three races positioned incumbent PM Benjamin Netanyahu and his Likud party, alongside other right-wing and religious parties, against a group of center-left parties, and particularly a new alliance called Blue and White, led by former Chief of Staff Benny Gantz. The first round (April 2019) resulted in a tie between Likud and Blue and White, and a failure of coalition negotiations that led to the second elections. In that round (September 2019), Blue and White emerged as the largest list, but neither Gantz nor Netanyahu was able to form a coalition. Following the third round (March 2020), where Likud emerged as the largest party, a short-lived government was formed, with Netanyahu as PM and Gantz as Alternate PM. Following the collapse of this unity government only eight months later, fourth elections were called (March 2021). This time, the constituent parties

of the Blue and White alliance ran separately, with Yesh Atid as the dominant party in the center-left camp, and its leader Yair Lapid as this camp's central PM candidate. While Likud won the largest number of seats and Netanyahu received the mandate to form a government, he failed to secure a majority. Eventually, Lapid was the one who managed to form a rotation government based on a broad coalition of eight parties, with Naftali Bennett (head of the small right-wing party Yamina) as the first PM and Lapid as alternate PM (to replace Bennett after two years).

To account for both the aggregate and interactional social dimensions of AF, we use a combination of surveys and focus groups with Israeli citizens. The eight pre-election and four post-election survey waves were administered throughout the four election rounds. The five focus group waves accompanied the first two rounds (see Figure 2).

Panel Survey

The initial survey wave was administered online to a representative sample of 1,191 Israeli citizens of voting age (wave I.1, declining to 688 by wave III.2 due to attrition, refreshed to 1,026 in wave IV.1; for details, see [Supplementary File I: Methodological Appendix](#)). The eight pre-election waves addressed participants' projections about the election results (expected largest party, PM, and coalition composition), including their predicted feelings about these outcomes. In this study, we focus on the PM projection, which is the more consequential outcome in the context of the fluid Israeli multiparty system. After predicting the identity of the next PM (choosing from a list of party leaders), we asked respondents: "Suppose that your forecast regarding the next PM is realized, how will you feel about this political reality?" Respondents predicted their feelings on a continuous slider ranging from "I will feel very bad" (0) to "I will feel very good" (100), with the midpoint (50; numerical values not shown) as neutral starting position (see [Fu et al., 2018](#) for a similar application; [Betella & Verschure, 2016](#) for the suitability of affective sliders; and [Gilbert et al., 1998](#), p. 623, for establishing the reliability and validity of single-item AF measures). Responses were recoded into variables that capture the intensity (the distance of expected affect from the midpoint) and valence (binary variable) of affective forecasts. In wave IV.1, we additionally asked participants to rate their affective forecasts concerning the possible victory of all major contenders

Figure 2. Timeline of Data Collection

Note: I–IV represent the election rounds; 1–3 represent the pre-election survey waves/focus group meetings within each round; P refers a post-election survey.

(rather than only participants' expected outcome). To assess the polarization of predicted feelings toward alternate outcomes at the individual level, we calculated the absolute difference between respondents' expected feelings about a possible victory of either incumbent Netanyahu or Lapid, his main challenger in election round IV.

To measure the extremity of political self-identification, we calculated the distance of participants' self-placement from the neutral midpoint on a slider ranging from "right" (0) to "left" (100). As Mason (2018) demonstrated, an ideological self-placement scale is adequate if not the ideal measure for identity-based ideology.

To assess exposure to politically congruent media, we created dummy variables based on (a) political self-identification and (b) two survey questions that asked participants to indicate which out of a detailed list of news outlets they used over the past week, and whom out of a detailed list of politicians they followed on social media. For the purpose of this study, we focused on exposure to three news outlets with well-known, pronounced political positions, especially concerning their alignment with the pro/anti-Netanyahu camps: the free newspaper *Israel Hayom* and television *Channel 20*, both of which supported Netanyahu, and the left-wing broadsheet *Haaretz*, which assumed a pronounced anti-Netanyahu stance.² Use of each news outlet was coded as politically congruent exposure (1) if respondents' political self-identification (right: 0–44 on the self-placement scale; left: 56–100) matched the leaning of the outlet (*Israel Hayom* and *Channel 20*–right; *Haaretz*–left). If respondents did not use a specific outlet or their political self-identification did not match the leaning of the outlet, it was coded as 0 (for similar procedures, see Tsfati et al., 2014; Tsfati & Chotiner, 2016). For social media, we focused on followers of Netanyahu and his main challenger in each round (Gantz, rounds I–III; Lapid, round IV), assuming both the centrality of candidates' social media communication in election campaigns and its provision of affective messaging regarding the candidate and his opponents (Enli, 2017; McLaughlin & Macafee, 2019). Following Netanyahu on social media was coded as politically congruent exposure (1) for participants who positioned themselves on the right, while following Gantz/Lapid was coded as 1 for those who positioned themselves on the left. Otherwise (not following the candidate; political self-identification not matching the candidate's camp), the value was 0.

In the pre-election surveys, participants' intention to vote was measured on a four-point scale from "definitely will not vote" to "definitely will vote." In the post-election waves, actual voting is treated as a binary variable (yes/no). Participants' gender, age, education level, religious identification, and interest in politics were included as control variables. [Supplementary File I](#) includes additional details on the measurement and variables.

Given the different availability of AF measures in the pre-election waves, hypotheses addressing the polarization of individuals' affective forecasts concerning alternate outcomes (H1b, H2a, H3b, H4c) were tested only for IV.1. All other hypotheses (H1a, H2b, H3a, H4a, H4b) were tested for all waves.

Focus Groups

To contextualize the survey data and examine the uses of AF in political discussions (RQ1, RQ2), we draw on 25 meetings of five focus groups, each convened five times over eight months, before and after election round I and before election round II. The groups included Israeli citizens—four groups of Jewish voters and one group of Arab citizens—of diverse gender, education, and political leaning (7–12 participants in each group). Each meeting lasted 90 min, and was conducted in a semi-structured fashion, designed to encourage natural conversation (Kamberelis & Dimitriadis, 2013). The open discussions in the focus groups revolved around the expected results and possible implications of the upcoming elections. Affective forecasts arose in the discussion both spontaneously and in response to moderators' direct questions. Most meetings started with the open question, "What do you think will happen in the upcoming elections?" Based on the ensuing discussion, we asked follow-up questions, including how the participants would feel about the realization of their predictions. The open-ended interactions enabled us to study how participants used and reacted to affective forecasts in the discussion, including unprompted AF.

The 25 focus group meetings were manually transcribed and were analyzed using the qualitative data analysis package MaxQDA, identifying a total of 108 interactions (1,291 turns) that referred to participants' expected future affect. Of these, 31 constitute responses to the moderators' direct prompting for affective forecasts, while the remaining 77 instances occurred spontaneously in response to other statements or questions. All interactions were inductively analyzed to unpack the roles affective forecasts played in the discussion. [Supplementary File I](#) includes further details on the sample, procedure, and analysis of the focus groups. Our findings are presented in the order of the hypotheses and RQs as outlined above.

Findings

Affective Forecasting, Social Identities, and Political Polarization

Social-Political Identities as Predictors of AF

First, we examined the contribution of political identities to AF about expected electoral outcomes (H1a). We conducted a set of regressions to predict the intensity of predicted feelings about the expected PM among our survey participants as a function of the extremity of their ideological self-identification. To separate the contribution of the level of political identification from that of different political leanings, participants' left/right identification was entered as a control variable alongside demographic variables. [Figure 3](#) presents the standardized regression coefficients for the role of ideological self-identification across waves (see [Supplementary File II](#) for the full eight models). Across all waves, the extremity of ideological identification significantly predicted the intensity of affective forecasts ($p < .001$). H1a is thus supported: the farther from the center a person positions herself on the ideological

Figure 3. Intensity of Affective Forecasts by Extremity of Political Identification across Waves: Projected Prime Minister (PM)

Note: $N=1,191$ (I.1), 996 (I.2), 932 (I.3), 770 (II.1), 813 (II.2), 708 (III.1), 688 (III.2), 1,026 (IV.1); Regressions controlled for gender, education, religion, age and left/right identification (see full models in [Supplementary File II](#)).

scale (whether to the left or to the right), the more intensely does she expect to feel about the projected electoral outcomes.

Second, to examine the relation between political identities and the polarization of individuals' affective forecasts regarding different possible outcomes (H1b), we used wave IV.1, where participants were asked about their expected feelings regarding a possible victory of different candidates (in addition to their projected PM). We regressed the absolute difference between participants' affective forecasts about Netanyahu and Lapid as PMs (i.e., level of polarization) on the same independent and control variables described above. Model 2 in [Table 1](#) shows the significant relationship between the extremity of participants' ideological self-identification and the polarization of their affective forecasts ($p < .001$). *H1b* is thus supported: the more extreme people's ideological identities are, the more polarized their affective forecasts are in relation to candidates from their own and others' political camps.

Uses of Affective Forecasting for Identity Work in Social Interaction

To understand if and how political identities are socially negotiated through affective social interactions (RQ1), we rely on the qualitative-inductive analysis of focus group interactions. This analysis revealed two primary interactional uses of AF for identity work: (a) positioning oneself within the group; and (b) managing inter- and intra-group relations.

Table 1. Regressions Predicting Polarization of Affective Forecasts (Wave IV.1)

Variables	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3		
	<i>B</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>p</i>
Step 1: Controls									
Rightwing	10.609	.151	.000	-4.566	-.065	.224	-7.334	-.104	.054
Leftwing	9.272	.114	.004	-4.522	-.056	.246	-3.955	-.049	.326
Education	-.817	-.033	.302	-.395	-.016	.613	-.596	-.024	.447
Religion	-3.289	-.081	.013	-4.454	-.110	.001	-4.104	-.101	.002
Age	.318	.136	.000	.335	.143	.000	.309	.132	.000
Gender	6.080	.087	.005	5.982	.085	.005	5.141	.073	.016
Step 2: Political identity									
Extremity of ideological identification				.512	.257	.000	.437	.219	.000
Step 3: Exposure to politically congruent media									
News-Channel 20 (right)							6.501	.043	.182
News-Israel Hayom (right)							5.174	.053	.115
News-Haaretz (left)							2.750	.017	.615
Social media-Netanyahu							9.972	.101	.003
Social media-Lapid							11.472	.046	.136
Adjusted R-squared	.039			.071			.084		

N = 1,026.

Positioning Work. Every spoken act of AF about election outcomes potentially contributes to situating the speaker politically, as it reveals the desirability of political futures from her perspective. Accordingly, it was a useful discursive tool in participants' self-presentation and in inferring who were the members of their in- and out-group(s). Take for instance the following interaction in the opening of the first group meeting (FG4, I.1):³

Moderator: As a starting point, we would love to know what do you think is going to happen in the upcoming elections?

Aliza (F, 58): In my opinion, the Likud will rise. [. . .]

Miriam (F, 35): I agree with her. To me it's sad, but I agree.

Aliza: I am very happy about it.

Ksenia (F, 52): To me it's also sad, but that's what will happen [. . .]

Tzlil (F, 41): I also agree that the Likud is going to . . .

Aliza: Ah, and you are also sad about it?

Tzlil: No, I am not sad about it. Because the country is relatively well run.

Aliza: Great.

Through negotiating the affective evaluation of the suggested scenario (that the ruling party will get stronger), the participants quickly position themselves in the group and identify their allies. Two subgroups rapidly emerged: those who expected to be happy about a Likud/Netanyahu victory and those who expected to be sad about it. The projection alone, without its affective dimension, would not allow this social alignment.

In groups where such positioning processes did not immediately take place, in-groups coalesced following direct AF questions. For instance, in response to our question concerning expected feelings about a Netanyahu victory (FG2, I.1), a group of young anti-Netanyahu participants provided a harmonized sequence of expected negative reactions, ranging from “disappointment” (Peleg, F, 24) and “great despair” (Meshi, F, 26), which directly expressed feelings, to AF formulated as behavioral intention: “I’m leaving the country” (Ofer, M, 28). This last reaction likely represented Ofer’s expected distress about the depicted scenario rather than an actual intention to emigrate. Notably, while there were Netanyahu supporters in the focus group, they refrained from taking part in this AF interaction, which served to establish a specific ingroup.

Managing inter- and intra-group relations. In subsequent focus group meetings, participants’ AF uses have shifted from self-positioning to negotiating the relations with members of their already-established out-group and in-group. A notable example is an interaction between Aliza, a strong Netanyahu supporter (see above), and two members from the anti-Netanyahu camp, just before the September 2019 elections (FG4, I.2):

Aliza: Imagine that in next month’s meeting, I will come in shame if Bibush [endearing nickname for Netanyahu] doesn’t win.

Ronen (M, 40): I don’t think you will be ashamed, even if Bibi [colloquial nickname for Netanyahu] doesn’t win. [. . .] You will get a hug from most of the people here, I promise.

Aliza: Really?

Yoel (M, 62): We will support you! [. . .] Will you also support us if we lose?

Aliza: No (everybody laughs).

Yoel: But we will support you, despite everything.

This interaction encapsulates a complex set of expected affective responses, combining shame, empathy, affection, and resentfulness. By imagining how participants will feel and react to one another following an electoral defeat of one of the sides, members of different political groups negotiate their relations. While Aliza seems to be touched by the gesture, a relational asymmetry is revealed when she does not reciprocate the message of solidarity expressed by members of her out-group. Nevertheless, participants’ laughs in response to Aliza’s reaction might suggest a different kind of group solidarity, where participants already know and accept one another. This type of acquaintance also led participants in various groups to

anticipate one another's affective responses during the discussion, as demonstrated in expressions such as "don't be offended" (Peleg, FG2, II.1) or "I am sorry to disappoint you" (Gloria, F, 51, FG1, II.2).

In addition to inter-group relations, AF was also used in negotiating intra-group identities. On the one hand, participants used affective forecasts to express solidarity with other in-group members—as did Peleg (FG2, MI.2), when she responded to an AF question tied to a poll indicating a lead for Netanyahu by pointing at Ofer (who had expected feeling unhappy about a Netanyahu win; see above) and humorously promising, "I'll help him pack." By remembering Ofer's previous response to a similar AF question ("leaving the country") and expressing her support, she affirms their in-group relations.

On the other hand, AF also served to negotiate in-group loyalties. For instance, when Tzlil, a Netanyahu supporter, said toward the second round of elections (FG4, II.1) that "it's not that clear that Bibi will be elected" and that she would feel bad if he lost, her fellow Netanyahu supporter, Aliza, admonished her that "if you felt bad about it you would be more decisive." And when Tzlil said in the meeting afterwards (II.2) that she believed Netanyahu would win, Aliza was still not satisfied, demanding: "say it happily!" Underlying these interactions is an implicit expectation of a match between people's political affiliation, electoral projections, and AF, as an expression of loyalty to the in-group.

Polarized Distributions of AF

The strong in-group–out-group distinctions that underlie AF's interactional uses are also evident at the level of the overall distribution of affective forecasts about different candidates. When survey participants were presented with different possible scenarios about the identity of the future PM and asked how they would feel about them (in wave IV.1), the distribution of affective forecasts for the main candidate in each camp (Netanyahu for the right-wing camp, Lapid for the center–left), had similar characteristics (see [Figure 4](#)): a bimodal distribution where the extreme negative and positive values (0 and 100, correspondingly) are the two most frequent AF values. At the same time, the greater emphasis in both cases is on the negative side (i.e., expecting to feel very unhappy about the depicted scenario). While views are slightly more polarized toward Netanyahu (Kurtosis: -1.6 ; for Lapid: -1.5), Kurtoses for both distributions are significantly below -1.2 (uniform distribution), indicating polarized distributions. H2a is thus supported.

A different pattern emerges when we examine people's actual electoral expectations and how they expect to feel about their materialization. [Figure 5](#) illustrates the underlying distributions, using the histograms of observed affective forecasts about the projected PM in wave II.2 (where kurtosis values were most representative of the prevalent patterns in election rounds I–III) and wave IV.1 (selected as direct comparison to [Figure 4](#)). Here we observe major differences between the distribution of affective forecasts about the incumbent (Netanyahu) and the challengers (Gantz in rounds I–III, Lapid in round IV). As seen in [Figure 5](#), among those

Figure 4. Histograms of Affective Forecasts about Competing Prime Minister (PM) Candidates

Figure 5: Histograms of Affective Forecasts toward Projected Prime Minister (PM)

respondents who expected Netanyahu to prevail, we find a bimodal, polarized pattern of affective forecasts: many respondents expect to feel extremely good about this prospect, and many others expect to be extremely unhappy. By comparison,

predicted affect is unimodal and heavily skewed among those who project a challenger victory, with most responses close to the positive end of the scale. That is, a victory of the incumbent is predicted by both Netanyahu's supporters and opponents, while a challenger victory is predicted almost exclusively by those who prefer this outcome. This finding is consistent across all waves (see [Supplementary File II](#)), supporting H2b: affective forecasts about expected political outcomes are more polarized in relation to incumbent leaders than to challengers.

Affective Forecasting and Exposure to Politically Congruent News and Social Media

To examine the role of politically-congruent media exposure, we regressed the intensity of AF toward the projected PM on participants' exposure to like-minded news and social media content, controlling for ideological self-identification (extremity and left/right) and demographics. [Figure 6](#) presents the standardized regression coefficients for exposure to politically congruent media across waves (see [Supplementary File II](#) for all models). Overall, the models are somewhat improved with the addition of the media variables, with an adjusted *R*-Squared for the full model ranging between .07 and .10 in the various waves. However, while exposure to at least one of the candidates' social media is a significant predictor in all waves except I.1, exposure to any of the politically congruent news outlets is not significantly associated with AF intensity. Hypothesis H3a is therefore only partially supported.

In Wave IV.1, before the fourth election round, only like-minded exposure to Netanyahu's social media messages significantly predicted the intensity of affective forecasts about the projected PM. Similarly, regarding the level of AF polarization, only following Netanyahu on social media is associated with increased contrast in people's assessments of their predicted feelings about victory of the two candidates, above and beyond the contribution of ideological self-identification (see [Table 1](#)). Accordingly, H3b is very partially supported.

Figure 6. Intensity of Affective Forecasts by Politically Congruent News/Social Media Exposure: Projected Prime Minister (PM)

Note: Non-shaded bars represent the significant predictors. *N* for each wave the same as [Figure 3](#) above. Regressions controlled for gender, education, religion, age, left/right identification, and extremity of ideological identification (see full models in [Supplementary File II](#)).

The Motivating Power of Affective Forecasting

The last step in the analysis concerns the behavioral implications of affective forecasts, and specifically their relation to political mobilization. At the individual level, we conducted a set of regressions to predict people's intention to vote (ordinal regressions within waves) and actual voting (logistic regressions combining pre- and post-election waves) as a function of the intensity (H4a) and valence (H4b) of predicted feelings about the projected outcomes, as well as the degree of polarization in affective forecasts (H4c). Across all eight pre-election waves, the intensity of affective forecasts is a significant predictor of intention to vote: the more intensely people expect to feel about electoral outcomes the more they are inclined to vote (see Table 2, Model A2 for Wave IV.1; Supplementary File II for all waves). For actual voting (Table 2, Model B2, Supplementary File II), the relationship's direction is maintained in all elections, but is significant only in the fourth round (likely due to the larger sample size in Wave IV.P in relation to other post-election waves and the binary voting measure's low variance). H4a is thus largely supported.

An examination of valence as a predictor of voting shows that across all waves, people who expect to be happy about the results (i.e., marked above 55 on the AF scale), tend to be more likely to vote than others, above and beyond the contribution of intensity (which is blind to the valence of AFs). However, valence was a significant predictor of intention to vote in only four out of the eight pre-election waves and a significant predictor of actual voting in one of the four election rounds (Table 2, Models A2/B2, Supplementary File II). H4b thus receives partial support.

The relation between turnout and the polarization of the affective forecasts was tested just for Wave IV.1 (Table 2, Models A3/B3), where polarization measures were available. The results show that the more polarized people's affective forecasts are regarding the victory of the opposing camp's main candidates, the more they are likely to vote. H4c is thus supported.

At the social interaction level, the relation between AF and political mobilization was examined using focus group data. There, AF was occasionally invoked as a mobilizing tool, employed by individuals to sway themselves or others toward certain actions, as evident in a meeting prior to the second elections (FG3, II.1):

Avraham (M, 30): Everybody here are surely going to vote? [. . .]

Hani (F, 49): I will not feel comfortable not to [. . .]

Dvir (M, 52): With effort, I swear to you, I don't feel like going.

Hani: Yes, I don't feel like it either.

Dvir: But I'm afraid that if I won't feel like it, and he won't feel like it, and she won't feel like it, we will eventually be sorry about that!

Here, participants explain their intention to vote by how bad they will feel if they abstain. Underlying this exchange is both a sense of civic duty (expecting to feel guilty) and a fear of regretting abstention, should the outcomes be undesirable. As in other domains, people propel themselves to do something despite their

Table 2. Regressions Predicting Intention to Vote (Wave IV.1) and Actual Voting (Ivs And Controls: Wave IV.1; DV: Wave IV.P)

DV	Model	Intention to vote			Actual voting		
		A1 Controls	A2 Affective forecasting (AF) intensity and valence	A3 AF polarization	B1 Controls	B2 AF intensity and valence	B3 AF polarization
		Odds ratio	Odds ratio	Odds ratio	Odds ratio	Odds ratio	Odds ratio
	Ideological identification	.992 ^{**}	.994 [*]	.996	.984 ^{***}	.988 ^{**}	.988 ^{**}
	Political interest	2.413 ^{***}	2.276 ^{***}	2.258 ^{***}	2.449 ^{***}	2.395 ^{***}	2.163 ^{***}
	Education	.715 ^{***}	.733 [*]	.723 ^{***}	1.181	1.235 [*]	1.202 [*]
	Religion	1.208 ^{**}	1.243 ^{***}	1.251 ^{***}	.722 [*]	.682 ^{**}	.724 [*]
	Age	1.022 ^{***}	1.021 ^{***}	1.018 ^{**}	1.025 ^{**}	1.019 [*]	1.021 [*]
	Gender (men)	1.034	.912	1.122	.624	.676	.564 [*]
	Intensity of AF (0–50)		1.029 ^{***}			1.019 ^{**}	
	Valence of AF (happy)		1.228			2.635 ^{***}	
	Polarization of AF			1.023 ^{***}			1.028 ^{***}
	Cox & Snell R-squared	.152	.088	.189	.113	.235	.148
	Nagelkerke R-squared	.189	.180	.235	.232	.292	.303

Notes: The table presents odds ratios from ordinal regressions predicting intention to vote in the survey before the fourth elections (N = 1,026) and from logistic regressions predicting reports on actual voting in these elections by predictors measured in the pre-election wave (N = 910).
^{***}p < .001, ^{**}p < .01, ^{*}p < .05

inclinations (e.g., exercise, diet) by simulating how good or bad they will feel afterwards. In case of voting, however, the scenario includes a collective dimension, imagining both how others will behave and what will be the subsequent (in)group feelings (“we will eventually be sorry about that”).

Similarly, AF was used to challenge existing perceptions and intentions. This was commonly done in the context of imagining the implications of not voting, either to encourage voting or, as in the meetings of Arab Israeli citizens, as part of the debate over boycotting the elections. For instance, when Dalal (F, 36, FG5) expressed her fear that by not voting, her community might lose effective representation in Israeli politics, participants negotiated the conditions under which such fears could be mitigated. Eventually, Dalal consented that if there were adequate alternatives to parliamentary representation, she “will not be feeling this danger.”

Finally, the close connection between AF, political mobilization, and efficacy is particularly evident when the option to act upon AF is unavailable. For instance, in the following excerpt, participants discuss the possibility that the challenger Gantz might join a Netanyahu-led coalition as Minister of Defense (a scenario that materialized about a year after this meeting):

Haim (M, 55): When you start asking what will happen, we are wasting time. [. . .] The PM decides who will be this or that minister. Even if all the people explode, we won’t change that. Until the ninth [of April, election date], we can do something. Afterwards – not!

Denis (M, 34): But Haim, how will you feel about it?

Haim: I won’t feel anything! Because I didn’t choose [the Minister of Defense]! I choose a government. The government chooses this or that minister. So why do you think I need to feel anything?

Zeev (M, 36): She [the moderator] asks, Haim, if you will feel betrayed [. . .]

Haim: I won’t feel anything! Because I feel until the ninth, and that’s it. (everybody laughs).

This revealing interaction follows a direct question by the moderator on how participants expect to feel about the depicted scenario (unlike previous examples, where AF was invoked spontaneously). Haim’s words underscore the connection between AF and engagement, suggesting that one should assess her/his future feelings about possible scenarios only when it can make a difference.

Discussion and Future Directions: Understanding Affective Forecasting as a Socio-Communicative Process

In this article, we have offered a socio-communicative perspective on AF in the context of political projections. Using the case of the 2019–2021 Israeli elections and a mixed-method approach, we have taken first steps in examining the socio-communicative predictors, manifestations, and consequences of AF, moving beyond the common focus on its accuracy. Specifically, we argue that when AF

addresses collective futures, predicted feelings cannot be conceptualized without considering their embedding within social identities and both interpersonal and public communication, along with their implications for political polarization and engagement. In this section, we discuss the findings and future research agenda, moving from the socio-communicative factors that shape affective forecasts, to their interactional uses and social implications.

Socio-Communicative Factors Shaping Affective Forecasting. Our analysis establishes the relation between people's political identities and their affective expectations. Beyond the obvious tendency to expect positive feelings regarding a preferred candidate's victory, predicted feelings were more intense and polarized among individuals with more extreme political identities. This significant and consistent relationship across all survey waves is particularly notable given the position of Israeli PM candidates on the moderate right and center-left of the political map, with the ideological spectrum extending much further in both directions. In the future, more nuanced measures should be considered to better capture the social-identity dimensions of political identification (Bankert *et al.*, 2017).

The relations between media exposure and AF are more complex. While we expected that exposure to politically congruent news and candidates' social media would lead to more intense and polarized affective forecasts, only the latter was significantly associated with AF, above and beyond the influence of political identities. There are several complementary explanations: first, in the complex Israeli political and media spheres, news outlets do not neatly map onto political preferences, especially within the center-left camp. While the left-leaning *Haaretz* newspaper has a distinct anti-Netanyahu editorial position, its alignment with more centrist candidates (Gantz and Lapid) is less clear-cut. Arguably, AF concerning a possible Gantz/Lapid victory may have been shaped more by centrist outlets (especially the mainstream TV news channels), even though these might have been less uniquely affiliated with either camp. To examine this possibility, a content analysis of these outlets is needed. Second, voters' positive and negative appraisals of the prospect of another Netanyahu-led government might have been already so ingrained by years of exposure to polarized public discourse that additional news coverage no longer intensified these feelings. Third, and relatedly, controlling for political self-identification may mask a more profound, cumulative role of the media environment, which reinforces political identities and feelings over time (Iyengar *et al.*, 2012; Slater, 2007). Therefore, the recorded political self-positioning may already reflect long-standing media influences upon the formation of affective forecasts.

Contrary to the news, whose influence on political AF might be nuanced and cumulative, it seems that exposure to preferred candidates' social media communication, with its strong emotional appeals and binary candidate portrayals, leads to significant contrast effects (see Banks *et al.*, 2021), and thereby more intense and polarized affective forecasts. Notably, while candidates' social media constitute a central channel of political campaigns, this study captures only a small portion of

the affective and polarizing discourse that people are exposed to online. To further understand the influence of both news and social media on AF, people's affective forecasts should be tied back to the affective content they encounter in both news and social media ("linkage studies"; de Vreese et al., 2017). To this end, sentiment analysis may help in mapping the valence and intensity of feelings expressed toward various actors and issues in politically mediated discourse (e.g., Young & Soroka, 2012). Linking AF to exposure to specific media contents in the periods between survey waves will also help in establishing causality and making full use of the panel design (used in the present article mainly for validation and robustness purposes).

Interactional Uses of Affective Forecasting. In addition to analyzing AF's socio-communicative predictors, we have demonstrated the use of AF for identity work in interpersonal communication. As the focus group analysis shows, people used AF for self-positioning, mobilizing, and managing political inter- and intra-group relations. Hence, similar to public opinion (Cramer, 2016; Price, 1992), AF can be conceptualized both as an aggregation of individual assessments and as a group-based discursive process. Future investigations should further explore AF's discursive uses, especially in more natural mediated and unmediated settings. Beyond providing a broader understanding of the discursive manifestations of AF, it can help disentangle the effect of the moderated focus group conversations on the uses of AF identified in this study. The range of negative and positive emotions identified in the discussions also underscores the need to include in future surveys measures of discrete emotions that go beyond the valence and intensity of AF (see Lecheler, 2018). More broadly, the study demonstrates the usefulness of bringing together the complementary methods of surveys and focus groups for studying the socio-communicative dimensions of phenomena that have both individual and interactional dimensions, and for understanding interpersonal communication within political communication processes (Shah et al., 2017).

Social Implications. Political polarization and participation emerged as two key social implications of collective AF processes. The analysis showed the strong polarization of AF in relation to the possible victory of candidates from different camps, as manifested in the overall distribution of AF across the electorate. It also established the greater tendency to vote among people with more intense affective forecasts, those who expect to feel happy about the outcomes, and those who have more contrasting affective forecasts about different candidates.

Considering previous literature that links both political polarization and participation to present feelings toward candidates/parties (e.g., Iyengar et al., 2019; Marcus, 2010), one important question that requires further examination concerns the relationship between present and forecasted feelings, and thus, the added value of AF in relation to existing affective measures in political contexts. Differences

between present and predicted affect may be especially pronounced when people need to imagine sociopolitical changes, and thus cannot readily extrapolate from current experiences, but rather need to rely on other heuristics and sources (e.g., media sources). The detected asymmetry in the distribution of AF, when tied to people's actual political expectations, underscores two important patterns in this context: the centrality of the present situation in people's assessments (most people predict a victory of the incumbent, with polarized AF), and the connection between positive AF and the motivation to imagine change (most people who predicted a challenger victory expected to feel good about it). These findings, together with the demonstrated relationship between AF and voting, suggest that engaging people in political projections—especially positive ones—might foster political participation. The media, as a central avenue for the construction and negotiation of political futures (Neiger, 2007; Tenenboim-Weinblatt, 2018) can play an important role in this process, which is yet to be investigated.

Finally, there is a need to extend the current study to other contexts. While the surveys yielded consistent results throughout the four consecutive rounds of elections, increasing our confidence in their generalizability, these are still unique circumstances. Given that patterns of political evaluation and polarization vary across locales (e.g., Reiljan, 2020; Suk *et al.*, 2020), we can expect such differences also in relation to future-oriented assessments. Comparative studies of elections worldwide can advance our understanding of AF dynamics in different political and media systems, and under different levels of uncertainty. Furthermore, studying AF in communication should extend beyond the context of elections—to areas such as health crises (e.g., projections about the Covid-19 pandemic) or environmental issues. Such investigations, as suggested in this article, will contribute to our understanding of the role that AF plays, and can play, in societies' efforts to shape their futures.

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Notes

1. We refer to polarization in two complementing senses: as the level of contrast between affective forecasts about the victory of competing candidates at the individual level, and as the overall bimodal distribution of people's affective forecasts across society.
2. The political leanings of *Israel Hayom* and *Haaretz* were documented in multiple studies on the Israeli news media during Netanyahu's term as PM (e.g., Grossman et al., forthcoming; Shultziner & Stukalin, 2021), and several studies on exposure to politically-congruent media relied on the pre-defined positions of these two outlets (e.g., Garrett et al., 2014; Tsfati & Chotiner, 2016). While comprehensive content analyses for *Channel 20* are not available to date (due to its young age and the complexities of analyzing TV news), it has been widely recognized as a pro-Netanyahu right-wing channel (e.g., Panievsky, 2020; Tsfati, 2017). Its senior journalists and hosts are known to publicly support Netanyahu—to the point that the host of the channel's flagship show promoted a recent rebranding (from *Channel 20* to *Now14*) by tweeting that “King Benjamin the First will arrive tonight at eight for an interview on the opening broadcast” (<https://twitter.com/yinonmagal/status/1464922256677773316?s=11>; originally in Hebrew).
3. The annotation marks the group (FG1–FG5) and wave (I.1–II.2; see Figure 2); gender and age of participants are marked upon the first mentioning of a name.

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